

Work Life Balance and Stress Level of Working Women in India

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1. INTRODUCTION

In the 21st century, women employees has become an important subject since the time has changed from earning the family living in today's world where both ,men and women equally share the responsibility of earning foe the betterment of their family life. Work life balance focuses on two main aspects called achievement and enjoyment, **Lakshmi & Gopinath, 2013**. Work life balance is not the outcome of individual efforts, it involve the efforts of the organization, the employee, the family and the society in which all are embedded. Technologies advancements and new invention have impacted the socio-cultural life styles in Indian homes in the midst of all this, the compelling needs for growth in all spheres, for individual as well as for organization has resulted in imbalance in the lives of the workforce, **Sundaesan, 2014**. Women have shown their presence in every thought. From spots to aeronautics, from politics to engineering, from medical professions to academics, women have contributed significantly in almost every field. Work life balance of women employee is viewed as an important domain of discussion among researchers in the few decades. Extra demands on female academic employees could contribute to their occupational stress and work life imbalance. This can ultimately give rise to negative consequences for achieving the organizational goals and meeting the needs of the employees working with them. Work life balance and job stress go parallel to each other. What seem to be important employees give on balancing their lives and effectiveness of workplace practices and policies in supporting them to achieve such a goal, **Zaheer & Darakhshan, 2015**.

International business report (IBR) **2012**, of business consultancy reveals that the proportion of Indian women was occupying senior positions in business has catapulted from 9% in 2011 to 14%. **Thakur & Geete, 2014** indicated that there are changes in large part due to a significant cultural shift in parental perspective that is, an increased acceptance of giving education to girls that allows for possibility of women working outside the home, contributing economically to the family and even pursuing career, **Vijaya Mani, 2015**. Work life balance is a concept that supports the efforts of employees to split their time and energy between work and the other important aspects of their lives. Employees who have the tool to balance their professional and personal lives are happier, healthier, and more productive, in addition to improving performance; many

young employees' places a high value on work life balance. **Shukla, 2016**.

Here "satisfaction and good functioning at work and at home, with a minimum of role conflict" women employee working and personal lives are just like the two side sides of a coin. Work life balance is not the outcome of individual efforts. It involves the efforts of the organization, the employee, the family and the society in which all are embedded, **Bansal and Raj, 2017**.

1.1. Research Aim

1. Impedimental investigation of work-life balance among the working women.
2. To Study the various factor like hours worked, work involvement and family responsibilities affect married working women's work-life balance

2. Review Investigations

Mani Vijaya (2013) revealed that role conflict, lack of recognition, organizational politics, gender discrimination, elderly and children care issues, quality of health, problems in time management and lack of proper social support are the major factors influencing the work Life Balance of women professionals in India. **Raya., Prabhak'ara, Delina, G., (2013)**, explores the tough challenges faced by working women in maintaining a balance between their personal and professional life. The various factors affecting the work-life balance of married working women have been examined in this study. Explore the tough challenges faced by working women in maintaining a balance between their personal and professional life. The various factors affecting the work-life balance of married working women have been examined in this study. **K. Santhana Lakshmi et. Al. (2013)** studies reveal that educational institutions, should address the Work Life Balance related issues among their staff, specifically women and take a holistic approach to design and implement policies to support the teaching staff to manage their work life balance which would add to the performance of these staff members. **Balaji R. (2014)**, researcher stated that Family–work conflict and work–family conflict are more likely to exert negative influences in the family domain, resulting in lower life satisfaction and greater internal conflict within the family. Variables such as the size of family, the age of children, the work hours and the level of social support impact the experience of Work family conflict and

Family work conflict. It is also significant to note the success level gained by women in career and family in spite of all the stress they undergo at work place. It is also important to consider the consequences these variables have on psychological distress and wellbeing of the working women. **Shobha Sundaresan (2014)** study reveal consequences of poor work-life balance are high levels of stress and anxiety, disharmony at home, experiencing job burnout and inability to realize full potential. They feel irritable and resentful often due to their inability to balance work and family life. The findings have implications for working women and provide insights into finding solutions to maintain healthy work life balance. **Anshu thakur, Vishal Geete (2014)** studies concluded women employees are mentally occupied about the office work devoting more time in office which affects their domestic responsibilities which affects their temperament. Even though they are handling both the responsibilities they are not satisfied with the office support in managing their domestic problems. Due to that their domestic problems affects their professional work and vice-versa. Although the reason for such lopsidedness may be due to the age group which they belong majority of them are between 25-35, their salary, experience and qualification. **Zaheer Asma, et. al (2015)** studies reveal that there exists a moderate-level of occupational stress and moderate-level of work-life balance amid female faculties in central universities of Delhi, India. Further it is observed that there is a strong negative relationship between Occupational Stress and Work-Life Balance. **Shukla, Shinu.(2016)**, researcher reveal the optimum level of stress of working women which indicates the work life balance between individual and organizational bases of stress management. Work-life balance is a daily effort to make time for family, friends, community participation, spirituality, personal growth, self care, and other personal activities, in addition to the demands of the workplace. Working women they would be able to know work life balance means making decisions around where, who and what you are going to sacrifice, because you cannot do it all. **Vijayan., Sony and Jones Mary Ann (2016)** studies that majority of the women professionals have expressed that they are not able to balance their work life and personal life because of work pressure and compulsory over time. Most of them miss quality time with their family and friends. Due to work life imbalance, they suffer from various stresses related diseases. From this study it is clear that work life imbalance is seriously affecting the life and career of every woman professional so that it has a major influence on their life. **N. Prabha, P. Nirmala (2016)**, studies has been identifying that most of the married working women struggling to balance their work and home to balance. They are paying less time in their home when compared to work. Married women are preferring job for their financial need and for their family support. And most has been stated that they are missing to take care of their children personally. Married woman employees in education sector are giving more importance to the factor financial need followed by Family support, Career growth, Independence and the least importance is given to avoid boredom at home, travelling time, Attending family function, working hours and the least importance for work environment. **Neeraja S. Iyer (2017)**, the stress and work pressure is far more than others as a lot of time management, job management, kid management, house management everything is put under criteria. It is critical for work and family research to fully understand the

conditions under which the married women employees experience conflict between their roles. **MS Narayana, J Neelima (2017)** women faced several problems but, significantly, most often the "break in their careers" arises out of motherhood and family responsibilities." Women employees working in the banking industry to maintain a balance of work can have serious implications on the life of an individual. Work and personal life conflict occur when the burden, obligations and responsibilities of work and family roles become incompatible, it is very difficult to balance home life and work life. In other words women employees of public sector banks are performing well on job knowledge, interpersonal relationship, while women employees of private sector banks are having an edge over their public sector counterparts in parameters like attitude towards work and ambition for career growth. **Ashok Kumar Bansal & Lekh Raj (2017)** study was conducted among 34 women employees working in I.O.C.L Mathura. women employees are not fully satisfied with IOCL policies of work life balance because IOCL only provide maternity leave policy only, it does not provide flexible working hours, job sharing option, paternity leave, time off for WLB and child care (crèches) which played an important role in balancing work and personal life **Barik Pratibha (2017)** studies has explored that both in government and private schools female married teachers are unhappy with work-life balance. But still they are struggling hard to somehow manage between work-life. In this adverse situation they have learn to manage their time efficiently. Further the research revealed that female workforce decides their priorities and accordingly they manage their time at home and school. They try to get household support from servants, parents/in-laws, and children and even from their husband. Apart from this they choice to work at their nearby school to save their travelling time. Sometimes stress provides positive outcomes. Stress can sometimes motivate and refresh and enable people to achieve more; the key appears to be in how individuals are able to cope with it. Both the sector can help working women by implementing organizational strategies to control or reduce some of the major causes of stress. **Tasnim Mayesha, Hossain Zakir Muhammed, Enam Fabiha (2017)**, studies has been conducted based on primary research where a sample of 40 female employees from different organizations shows that the reasons for which female employees are facing trouble to maintain a work-life balance are mostly because of: long working hours, job rigidity, work overload, responsibilities related to child care, discrimination & biasness at work place, lack of supervisory support, dominant managerial style and scarce family support.

Research Methodology

Data Collection

The questionnaire was administered to the randomly selected married working women of the various sectors in Prayagraj (Allahabad), Lucknow and Kanpur Uttar Pradesh. A total of 151 check list instruments were distributed and 110 completely filled questionnaires were collected giving an overall response rate of 73 per cent.

Scope

The scope of the study was limited to the married working women of Prayagraj (Allahabad), Lucknow and Kanpur from the academic, nursing, advocate, and police sectors regarding the challenges that they face in balancing professional life and personal life.

Data Analysis and interpretation

Mean and Standard Deviation: The mean and standard deviation of responses (based on agreement of respondents) for each statement in the checklist are tabulated as below: *(Variables used for this study were already tested by the G.Delina (2013))*

Descriptive Statistics							
Variables		N	Min	Max	Mean		Std. Deviation
		Statistic	Statistic	Statistic	Statistic	Std. Error	Statistic
1	At the moment, because the job demands it, I usually work long hours (WLH)	110	2	5	4.29	.068	.708
2	There isn't much time to socialize /relax with my partner/see family in the week (MTS)	110	1	5	4.20	.096	1.003
3	I have to take work home most evenings (TWH)	110	1	5	3.41	.127	1.329
4	I often work late or at weekends to deal with paperwork without interruptions (OWL)	110	1	5	3.56	.134	1.405
5	Relaxing and forgetting about work issues is hard to do (RF)	110	1	5	4.16	.085	.894
6	I worry about the effect of work stress on my health (EWS)	110	1	5	4.10	.098	1.031
7	My relationship with my partner is suffering because of the pressure or long hours of my work (LHW)	110	1	5	3.86	.113	1.185
8	My family are missing out on my input, either because I don't see enough of them/am too tired (MFM)	110	1	5	4.26	.090	.945
9	Finding time for hobbies, leisure activities, or to maintain friendships and extended family relationships is difficult (FTH)	110	2	5	4.36	.068	.713
10	I would like to reduce my working hours and stress levels, but feel I have no control over the current situation (NC)	110	2	5	4.38	.067	.704
	Valid N (list wise)	110					

Among all of the statements presented in Table, the statement "I would like to reduce my working hours and stress levels, but feel I have no control over the current situation" and Finding time for hobbies, leisure activities, or to maintain friendships and extended family relationships is difficult" The statements had closer mean scores of 4.38 and 4.36 respectively which implies that married working women find it hard to reduce working hours and family relationship because of their tight schedules working hour and they feel helpless as they feel they do not have any control over their working hours and stress levels. The next mean scores of 4.29 and 4.26 were for the statements "At the moment, because the job demands it, I usually work long hours" and "My family are missing out on my input, either because I don't see enough of them/am too tired feel worried about the effect of work stress on their health". The next statements "I worry about the effect of work stress on my health" have mean score 4.20. "There isn't much time to socialize /relax with my partner/see family in the week" and "Relaxing and forgetting about work issues is hard to do" have the mean scores of 4.20 and 4.16 respectively. "My relationship with my partner is suffering because of the pressure or long hours of my work" have mean score 3.86 it implies that most of the working women are dual career couple. On the other hand, "I have to take work home most evenings" and "I often work late or at weekends to deal with paperwork without interruptions" scored 3.56 and 3.41. The lowest mean score, 3.41, which implies that the majority of respondents didn't take work home in the evenings.

Hypothesis testing:

Hypothesis- : 1. Alternative Hypothesis (H₁): There is significant relationship between working long hours and work life balance.

Null Hypothesis (H₀)₁: There is no significant relationship between working long hours and work life balance.

Correlations			
		work life balance	At the moment, because the job demands it, I usually work long hours
Work life balance	Pearson Correlation	1	.667**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
	N	110	110
At the moment, because the job demands it, I usually work long hours	Pearson Correlation	.667**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	
	N	110	110
**. Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).			

The correlation value of long working hours and work life balance was found to be 0.667 such moderately high value is indicative of the fact that a significant impact is made by long working hours is ensuring work life balance.

Hypothesis:- 2

- 1. Alternative Hypothesis (H₁):** Work life balance is significantly impacted by family responsibility & commitment.
- 2. Null Hypothesis (H₀):** Work life balance is not significantly impacted by family responsibility & commitment

		work life balance	Finding time for hobbies, leisure activities, or to maintain friendships and extended family relationships is difficult
work life balance	Pearson Correlation	1	.421**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
	N	110	110
Finding time for hobbies, leisure activities, or to maintain friendships and extended family relationships is difficult	Pearson Correlation	.421**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	
	N	110	110

The correlation value of family responsibility and commitment was found to be 0.421. Such moderate positive value indicates that family responsibility and commitment ensuring work life balance.

Findings

On the analysis of data reveal that due to demand of job women have spent long hour in their office due to long working hour have increase the risk of psychosocial stress and health problem. Long working hours could lead to tiredness, fatigue and lack of attentiveness towards the children. Naturally the more hours in office, the less time spend with family or other leisure activities want to reduce their stress level and working hours but they have no control over the current situation. Women are not finding time for hobbies, leisure activities and to maintain friendships and family relationship Forgetting about work issue due to combination of all things happening all at once and sometime spillover on speaking Most of the time children and family member are missing they are not able to spent time Women agree their counter-part are in the profession they do not feel relationship are suffer

Conclusion

Present study measured the work-life balance of working married women. Most of them were belongs nursing, academic and banking sectors. This study finds out that the respondents were managing the family responsibility and

commitment towards their professions by ensuring the harmonious family life. As per findings of present study responded reflected relationship with work life balance and their stress level. Their relationships with partners were not suffered highly in case of both are in the profession. Organizational long working hours affect negatively their stress level; most of the time respondent feels no control over the current situation. This study can be concluded that in the Indian context to maintain a balance between work and life is a challenge. As a consequence women suffer from job burn-out, experience high levels of stress and anxiety, are unable to realize their full potential and also do not enjoy harmonious family life. This study has revealed that, women responsible for their family and career is rarely given top priority women’s settle Family life with the help of ‘mother’ or ‘mother in law’. They also give quality time to children and not able to give priority to promotions or career growth.

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